

Madras Museum: Cultural Treasure of Tamil Nadu, India

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ABSTRACT

This article mainly discussed about the importance of Madras museum, and becomes the treasure of culture and heritage in Tamil Nadu. Museums are the agents of transformation and development, which reflects like the mirror of the society. Indeed, Museums could be the primary institutions that can foster peace. Every nations heritage and culture are easily promoted by the Government through museums, anybody can get knowledge about the culture from each region in one nation. The properties were used by the ancestors of the country may preserved under the guidance of Archaeological department through museums, could survived long period. On the consequences, Madras museums had enormous antiquities from ancient to modern period, which displayed proper manner. Nevertheless, the Madras museums might be the treasure of cultural antiquities which aware the people and safeguard the antiquities to the next generation.

Keywords: Government Museum, Archaeological antiquities, Cultural treasure, Excavation and Exploration.

Introduction

Tamil Nadu is situated in the southern part of India, possessed unique history to compare with other states. Archaeological antiquities belong to Archaeological excavation, and exploration by the Government, both individual scholars exhibits the heritage and culture of the region in high esteem. These archeological antiquities were collected in the archeological sites, which conserve by the scholars and preserved in the museum through display method. People around the world have enthusiastically made plan to visit the local museums and museums exists other parts. Museums are the recorded, preserved, remembered the artifacts preservation. Museums are the real place those who have seen all the culture from all over Tamil Nadu in one place. Some of the museums may preserve the artifacts as it is which discovered. During the British period, the museums are founded in India, which exists till date. One of the important aspects of maintaining cultural attributes through documentation of life and livelihood of the people from ancient to modern Tamil Nadu. Also the prominent merits of the museums could be preserve the ancient culture and civilization, like rituals, religion, gastronomy, art, architecture, numismatics and etc., Indeed, the every artifacts, works of art, musical instruments from museums could be the tool to exhibit the culture. On the path, the Madras museums are important place in Tamil Nadu, which exhibit heritage and culture. This article mainly discussed about the importance of Madras museum, and becomes the treasure of culture and heritage in Tamil Nadu

Nomenclature of Museum

The word Museum denoted from the Greek term ‘mouse’ which means the ‘seat of muses’. Also it indicates the temple of muses, with learning the fields of history, oratory, poetry, dance, comedy and astrology. The mythological version speaks that muses are the daughter of almighty Zeus, the Greek Jupiter.¹ A museum tells the story of world and region. It narrates how the living being has survived in its environment through the years. It could be the treasure house in culture and prominent soul of the nation.² Museum is the biggest institution that conserves the collection of artifacts and other objectives of some of the important fields like historical and scientific nature.³ There are numbers of Museums have been established for conserve the historical and archaeological goods on permanent or temporary nature. Mostly, the museums are

prevailed in the cities and towns of the nation, while million of the local people visited in the town's basically personal perspective, also eagerly visit the museums in India. Museums have established different objective where the researchers and specialists to aware the people through the antiquities. The prominent goal of museums has serving researchers in incredible shifting and serving the general public.

Museum and Culture

Museums are the store house of artefacts, which might be the important tourist place all over the world. Both domestic and foreign visitors eagerly wanted to visit the museums to know about the rich artistic and cultural heritage of country through the ages. In Archaic period, Chinese travelers visit India to know about the religion and culture, which existed on it.⁴ Perhaps, the Buddha relics were stored in the Buddihst mutt on those days. Moreover, they were witnessed about the ancient cities like Madras, Madurai, Thanjavur, Kachipuram, and Mahabalipuram.⁵ Tamil Nadu is famous for its culture. Nevertheless, the heritage monuments are preserved through museums in Tamil Nadu depicts the ancient culture ever. The Government Museum, Chennai are persevered by the Central Government of Archaeology might be oldest and most preserved museums in Tamil Nadu. Some of the sections also exhibit the archeology, arts history and science related messages.⁶ No doubt, Museums are the biggest tool to preach the culture to the modern generation.

Madras museum and its origin

During the colonial period, the Madras Literary society has involved to begin the museum campaign under the auxiliary of the Asiatic society from London at Madras. Then they found the Museum of Economic Geology in present Chennai.⁷ The society belongs to the Madras has demanded for the formation of Museum in Madras which objective to break the economic distress in the presidency, and eager to develop the non-agricultural resources which help the people to found the economic enhancement.⁸ Henry Chamier, a member of the council has recommended Madras Literary society for the foundation of Museums particularly benefitted for the students and scholars, which supported by the court of Directors on 28th February 1844. In 1851 A.D., the court of Directors from East India Company has accepted the offer the Surgeon Edward Green Balfour to be the honorary officer in charge of the Madras central Museum in the

college at Fort St George at Nungambakkam. In 1821 A.D., the college had been founded and made significant contribution to the enhancement of South Indian Languages.

The Museums was founded in the first of floor of the institution which exists in the Fort St George campus.⁹ Earlier, the notification revealed in the Fort St George Gazetteer on 29th 1851 A.D., becomes the first announcement regarding the opening ceremony of the Madras Government Museum.¹⁰ It gradually developed and extender under the management of directors and superintendents. The Government Museum, Chennai was founded in 1851 at the campus of Fort St George, near college road in Nungampakkam. Then it could be shifted to the present complex at Pantheon Road. The Museum complex consisting of six buildings and galleries covers an area of around 16.25 acres of land.¹¹ The objects displayed in the museum preserves a variety of artifacts and objects covering diverse fields including Art, Archeology, Bronze, Numismatics, Zoology, Natural history, Sculptures, Palm-leaf manuscripts and Amravati Paintings. It had steadily developed and expanded under the guidance and supervision of successive able directors. Beginning as a Museum of practical Geology, its scope was soon extended to cover other fields such as Archaeology, Ethnology, Pre-history and Natural History.¹²

Antiquities

There are lots of section in the Museums, which having one of the important section namely 'Archaeological section', where numerous prominent antiquities grasped from the excavation sites from South India. These antiquities properly preserved and displayed by the authorities on the same. The Archaeological antiquities consisted several sculptures, metal works, stone tablets having epigraphical sources. Most of these antiquities tells about the social history of inhabitants lived in this region. The Section also features a sizable collection of objects that showcase the industrial arts, including as wood carving, ivory work, metal ware, inlay, and embossed works, for which South India has long been renowned.¹³

Bronze figures

The metal figures are by far the section's most well-known items. Over 1500 of them may be found at the museum, of which roughly 85 are Buddhist, about 20 Jain, and the remaining 1000 are Hindu. This museum may be the only place on earth where such a sizable collection of

metal statues is gathered under one roof. It is important to keep in mind that South India is home to countless statues of this type. This staggering amount alone will demonstrate the depths to which the technique of casting metal figures or images had previously been practiced in this region of India, unheard of in the history of any other nation.

They are among the best works of art in the world since many of them are so well crafted and adhere to established aesthetic standards. Artifacts from many historical eras, such as the early Christian era and more modern times, are included in the bronze figure collection. The earliest Buddha statues date to the third century AD; four incomplete figures were found at Amaravati in the Guntur region. The appearance and characteristics of these figures reveal a high level of aesthetic knowledge on the part of their designers. The other, older Buddhist metal sculptures come from Nagapattinam and range in age. The tiny statue of Simhanada in the graceful Maharajah Lila stance and the Buddha in the seated position stand out among these.

Ethnographic collections

The first person to buy the ethnographic collections was Dr. Edward Thurston. The decorative arts of South Indian tribes including the Todas, Kotas, Mannas, Kanikar, Chenchus, Lambadis, Savaras, Khonds, and Gadabas are displayed in these collections. The collection consists of cult objects, farming and hunting gear, and models of tribal homes. Writing implements, tribal weaponry, decorations from the Todas, Kadar, and Lambadis, and other ethnographic collections can be found in the Ethnology Gallery. Among the assortment of south Indian musical instruments, the Pancha Mukha Vadyam is a unique and unusual exhibit that serves as a representative sample. Other noteworthy displays include shadow-play figures, a Meriah sacrificial post, and votive offerings presented to gods and goddesses at shrines in Christianity, Hinduism, and Islam.¹⁴

During 1960s, the ethnographic collections of the Ethnology Gallery were reorganized and new, modernized showcases were built up. The Anthropological galleries currently occupy nine halls of the Front Building. The galleries on the first floor have exhibits related to folk arts, physical anthropology, musical instruments, and ethnology, while the galleries on the lower floor feature prehistoric artefacts, weapons, and puppets. The following web sites for the Galleries of

Musical Instruments and Ethnology include slide shows as one of the unique features. As a result, it is possible to examine the items with supporting evidence.¹⁵

Art Section

The Chennai Museum has several traditional and modern paintings and sculptures on display. modern works in the media of oil, tempera, watercolour, graphics, and acrylic, as well as paintings from the Tanjore, Rajput, Moghul, Kangra, and Deccani styles. Contemporary metal sculptures and graphic arts are also included in the collections. Tanjore paintings depict situations from Tamil literature's Puranic (mythological) literature as well as the likenesses of Tanjore Maratha Kings and Queens. The sixteenth and seventeenth centuries AD are when the Rajput art was created. They illustrate the rhythm of love using musical modes. The court scene of Emperor Babur, as well as portraits of Jehangir and Shah Jehan, as well as animals and birds, is among the subjects of Moghul paintings. The principal subject matter of the Kangra paintings is Krishna tales. The collections contain twelve portraits of British governors and governors-general.¹⁶

Numismatics

Numismatics is the study of coinage. It is essential to the study of history, especially ancient history. It changes, embellishes, and even confirms history. A nation's political and economic history is largely constructed through numismatics, and these findings frequently support or contradict historical accounts. We have a plethora of knowledge about the government, historical geography, and religious history of ancient India because to numismatics. The Government Museum in Chennai includes a vast collection of gold, silver, copper, lead, potion, and billion-dollar coins from ancient, mediaeval, and modern India. A sample collection of foreign coins is available in addition to these.

Geological models

The majority of the general geological display consists of line drawings and visual exhibits, including a model of the world, the solar system, rivers, glaciers, and the consequences of earthquakes and volcanoes.¹⁷

Zoology

The Government Museum in Chennai's eleven-room long zoological galleries is next to the sculpture galleries of the Archaeological division. In the first floor galleries, invertebrates and fish are on show, while the exhibits on the ground floor concern skeletons, dentitions, reptiles, birds, mammals, and some foreign animals.¹⁸

Botany

Because so many items on which we rely have some type of plant origin, the importance of plants in daily life cannot be emphasized. The Systematic Botany and Economic Botany galleries are where the majority of the botanical specimens are shown. The exhibits in the Systematic Botany Gallery are grouped in the sequence of their evolutionary development, starting with the earliest Cryptogams, which include algae and fungi. The categorization scheme proposed by Bentham and Hooker is used to group flowering plant families. The models of various forms of inflorescence, ovules, pollen grains, and embryo sacs are exhibited with informative labels in the morphology section. Photographs, moist specimens, and preserved herbariums are examples of Systematic Botany specimens.¹⁹

Conclusion

Museums are the agents of transformation and development, which reflects like the mirror of the society. Indeed, Museums could be the primary institutions that can foster peace. Every nations heritage and culture are easily promoted by the Government through museums, anybody can get knowledge about the culture from each region in one nation. The properties were used by the ancestors of the country may preserved under the guidance of Archaeological department through museums, could survived long period. On the consequences, Madras museums had enormous antiquities from ancient to modern period, which displayed proper manner. Nevertheless, the Madras museums might be the treasure of cultural antiquities which aware the people and safeguard the antiquities to the next generation.

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